

Marketing Strategy to increase sales during a new normal era on PT. Promedika Mitra Utama (Distributor in the Medical Device Sector)

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ABSTRACT

COVID-19 has affected all economies. increases demand in Southeast Asia, particularly Indonesia, notably in the health and pharmaceutical industries, which grow significantly. Some entities like micro-retailers hope to make a profit. Micro retailers dominate Indonesian based on product sales. Micro retailers sales and revenue rise significantly. Promedika Mitra Utama (PMU) sells and marketing their product using B2C business model. as micro retailer categorizes in micro in medical device industry, PMU has also been affected positively and negatively by the pandemic. In 2023, market condition of medical devices had started to fall, this caused corona cases to have gone down, people don't really need medical devices. PMU as a micro retailer experienced a decline in sales as well, Learn from this dynamic condition. PMU wants to maintain the stability of sales performance at least will be stable to for a next a few years as a player on health and pharmaceutical industries. Marketing activities are one of those that can aid in this regard and directly relate to sales. In general, PMU has carried out marketing activities, but that kind of marketing activities PMU running are poor on measurement and monitoring, this led to his marketing activities often ineffective in Budgeting, scheduling, utilization. Entering 2023, PMU wants to make a marketing plan approach to efficiently budget campaigns, promotions, and other marketing activities according to the company's goals and objective. Good marketing plan approach will be anticipated volatility of the market by enhancing sustainable competitive advantage. and evaluating ongoing marketing activities. Using the AFI analysis framework based on internal, external, and SWOT formulation, will result in some proposed marketing planning strategy. Marketing plan will be used for 2023 and for 2024 input evaluation, where the results are in the form of a formulation of 7Ps of marketing mix, TOWS, and Porter Generic analysis. Finding of this research, it was found that PMU will plan and applied some strategy and policies offline and online-based marketing activities in 2 semesters during 2023. Which is the goal of the first semester to build awareness and Second semester will be discount incentives to boost sales.

KEYWORDS: COVID-19; Micro-Retailers; Medical Devices; Strategy; Marketing Plan; Indonesia

1. INTRODUCTION

COVID-19 has affected the economies of all countries. This supports demand in Southeast Asia including Indonesia to increase especially in the Health and Pharmaceutical Industries tend to grow rapidly¹ Customers are blindly looking for all medical needs² and some entities hope to make a profit. Micro retailers dominate Indonesian marketplaces based on product sales. During the epidemic, micro retailers' sales rise significantly. Medium merchants' revenue growth is smaller than micro retailers. It's a good sign for internet retailers ³Promedika Mitra Utama (PMU) sells and marketing their product using B2B and B2C business model. as one of the stakeholders that categorize in micro retailers as well in medical device industry has also been affected positively and negatively by the pandemic. For example, a pandemic causes the price of medical devices to be sensitive, strains medical device supply networks as shifting demand causes widespread shortages. Supply chain experience uncertainty several times because it is price sensitive and ultimately makes a cut loss, causing medical equipment to suffer losses. but the bad impact is directly proportional to the good impact felt, as likes experienced a sharp increase of sales from previous years, this is indirectly highly beneficial for the company performance. that it works toward through its day-to-day operations, success in this endeavor depends on the organization's ability to adapt to new circumstances⁴.

In 2023, market condition of medical devices had started to fall, this caused corona cases to have gone down, people don't really need medical devices. PMU as a micro retailer experienced a decline in sales as well. Learn from this dynamic condition. PMU wants to maintain the stability of sales performance at least will be stable to for a next a few years. Marketing activities are one of those that can aid in this regard and directly relate to sales. In general, PMU has carried out marketing activities, but that kind of

marketing activities, PMU running are poor on measurement, monitoring, and targeting their segmentation. this led to his marketing activities often ineffective in Budgeting, scheduling, utilization. Entering 2023, PMU wants to make a marketing plan approach to efficiently budget campaigns, promotions, and other marketing activities according to the company's goals and objective. Good marketing plan approach will be anticipated volatility of the market by enhancing sustainable competitive advantage. Moreover, the marketing plan will help PMU to organize the marketing activities, so it can be measured and monitor properly. so that in the future it can help accelerate the growth of sales performance and marketing activities themselves for this research, the data collection conduct primary, and secondary data on PMU. As like the current condition of marketing activities, what marketing platforms and channels are used, customer profiles, and what factors cause the rise and fall of marketing performance in PMU

2. BUSINESS ISSUE

Essentially, the company recognizes that the medical device market opportunity will continue to grow even after the pandemic and the new normal are over. However, disease continues to spread due to field conditions that are difficult to predict, particularly in the world of health. become pomegranate. A comprehensive evaluation of the company's consumer marketing strategy is required so that the products offered to the medical device market can be distributed and communicated accurately according to the targeted market. An antigen checking (alat rapid) tool is an example of a product that has become a pomegranate due to a temporary trend corona pandemic. This product is in high demand in some cases due to an increase in cases of covid. However, when pandemic ends the company does not integrate promotions and existing stock. This item is often overstocked, so that to avoid further losses, the company sells it at a low price. As shown in Figure 1 (left) sales of rapid test peaked in February 2021 and will keep going until July 2022, when the time from post-pandemic to endemic. Many factors contribute to the fluctuating sales trend.

Figure 1 Sales 2021-2022 antigen checking tool (left) sales contribution on some category (right)

Many factors contribute to the fluctuating sales trend. Among other things, because that year and month were in the early stages of the new variant of the Covid-19 outbreak around the world, many people carried out preventive activities in the form of prevention by using the corona rapid test. However, this is only one case in PMU that is a quandary; other categories of goods have many inequalities in sales conditions until 2022 in several other categories, shown on figure 1 (right). Some are relatively stable and predictable, while others are not. The company still frequently loses focus in communicating marketing activity convert to sales in specific categories as a source of revenue. reveal a reduction and imbalance in sales contribution in specific product categories, which supports sales instability., the company realizes that the category that still exists until now after the pandemic is one of the mask categories. Sales inequality in certain product categories has been a concern since the beginning of the pandemic. To face a market with high vitality, PMU at least must prepare for proper marketing plan strategy, to ensure their level of sales will be sustained to stable. and to proof downtrend sales of PMU here is Figure 2 is recapitulation overall sales on 2021-2022 down to 31% compare from last year (2021)

	B2C Sales Revenue	
	2021	2022 (End of Dec 2022)
Shopee	Rp 379,326,230	Rp 564,781,330
Tokopedia	Rp 59,955,554	Rp 142,325,217
Others (Retail to Store & other ecommerce)	Rp 8,393,584,700	Rp 5,358,723,511
Total	Rp 8,832,866,484	Rp 6,065,676,537

Table 1 B2C Sales Revenue on PMU 2021-2022

The problem faced by PMU is due to delays in marketing planning from management that has not prioritized the importance of marketing planning. This has been going on since PMU marketing activities began. This problem needs to be fixed because, in the future, it can help PMU maintain its position as a major player in the industry. In short, the study needs to find answers to three research questions:

1. What is proper proposed marketing strategy for PMU to optimizer their sales?
2. What is proper content for PMU corresponds to their target market?
3. What are measurement tools to monitor and evaluating the result of marketing activities?
4. PMU After proposing strategy, what recommendation implementation plans for PMU defining strategies?

3. METHODOLOGY

This research will be used qualitative analysis to assess internal, external, and audit marketing activites that PMU has been done before.

Figure 3. Conceptual framework (methodology)

The conceptual framework used in this study is the AFI framework on Figure 3, where there are 3 steps to perform the analysis. i.e.,

1. The analysis strategy includes internal and external analysis processes, then the results of the analysis are formulated into several strategies that are tailored to the needs and problems of the company in stage

2. Strategy formulation and then ends with the implementation plan

The primary data for this study will come from a combination of in-depth interviews, observation, internal/external platform data. conducted with relevant PMU Staff. Due to its significance in providing pertinent context. to the business environment in which

PMU operates, secondary data is just as crucial as primary data for this study. Deductive analysis will be used to look at the data that was collected. Some of the analytical theories described in the figure 3 above are methods where relevant marketing theories are used to analyse the facts that have been gathered. Segmentation, Targeting, and Positioning (STP) Analysis, Internal Audit Marketing activities according to Chaffey ⁵ on Books Digital Marketing on theory Situation Analysis, 7Ps Marketing mix, and Resource-based View (RBV) using the VRIO framework were used for the internal analysis of this research. In contrast, the external analysis of this study is founded on the Political, Economic, Social, Technology, Environmental, Legal (PESTEL), Porter's Five Forces, Competitor analysis, etc. After the analysis, PMU will be provided with an integrated marketing communication strategy based on SWOT and TOWS matrix to help them reach a greater number of their target consumers and sales. Also proposed marketing Mix and Porter generic to sharpening the overall marketing plan strategy.

4. FINDING AND ARGUMENTS

4.1 External analysis

This paper is based on situational analysis using observation data from internal company the external analysis will be used PESTLE, Porter 5 Forces, and Competitive analysis conducted on Table 2

Table 2. PESTLE Analysis (external)

Political	Economic	Social	Technology	Legal	Environment
Annual budget policy for Public Health Sector (Puskemas/Posyandu), suburb funding, and the pandemic PMU should prepare for the needs of the commodities also to start earlier for relation to government	Economic growth supported by economic acceleration through the reopening public activities will boost more micro business sector's viability and strength. Therefore, the government is preparing a new priority budget for the needs of puskemas and others. PMU must diversify its products and capture needs that are not dependent on corona needs anymore	Lower-to middle class the consumer expects a service that is simpler, faster, and less expensive, as well as accessible wherever and whenever they desire.	Based on Research from the United Nation (2021) explaining that micro-retail segments can adopt technology through Social Messaging and social media; these results show that Micro Customers can strengthen their business by leveraging digital tools with basic basics on the applications they use or consider important as business support.	PMU had been done 1 of 2 certifications legal.it is still a long permit process. still risky for PMU because it does not follow applicable standards	big flood in Samarinda, customers cannot visit the store or even want to deliver using local couriers such as Go-send by GoJek and other online motorcycle delivery services. This will shut down operations for a moment, but it can happen at any time

Table 3. Porter Analysis (external)

New Entrants (medium)	Supplier (low)	Buyer (medium)	Substitute Product/Service (high)	Rivalry Competitor (high)
It might be claimed that capital is a barrier to entering this market because it is highly expensive to start a business and become well established in a medical device sector like PMU. However, since central distributors have the authority to choose who will sub-distributor advertise their products, rivals can't be easy to access to vendors. vendor restricts one area to having only one approved agent to advertise their products. PMU keeps attempting different business models that are challenging for new entrant trying to compete	For operational and customer services, like Distribution Channel, IT Applications, ERP, Product and so on, PMU still depends on needs third-party providers. This supplier comes from several supply companies. There are a lot of them, and they are all different. PMU had set up good internal rules and organizational skills for dealing with third parties. So, suppliers don't have much negotiating power because they must go through several steps before they can sign contracts with the PMU	Lower-to middle class the consumer expects a service that is simpler, faster, and less expensive, as well as accessible wherever and whenever they desire.	Since most medical device products and services offer the same characteristics, there are many options for substitution. For example, during the last pandemic, all depended on the needs of the pandemic and corona. When the transition to endemic sector returns to daily health needs, such as Health Monitoring Tools, Public Health Canter needs, And Home care. But still this must be prepared by PMU to increase the completeness of its products so that it will bring more traffic to find out more PMU.	In general, there are competitors who have considerable capital power; however, they are only interested in mastering the B2B market. Therefore, if the PMU truly want to compete on a national scale, further divergence must be considered. perhaps more unique that has been done now. There is intense competition among medical devices company in Indonesia's target market.

Table 4. Competitor Analysis (external)

Company Aspect	PMU	Alkes Hidup Bahagia	Hygea Sumber Bintang	Klinik Apotik Ibnu Rusyd
Key competition advantage	Complete product SKU and Fairly aggressive mass marketing on online platform	Have a strong B2B relationship	Have a strong B2B relationship	has a specialization in the field of health services
Marketing communication	Facebook, IG, Pinterest, LinkedIn, LINE@, TikTok, Twitter, YouTube, Expo events, and Flyer Sign.	Facebook, IG, TikTok, Twitter, Expo events, and Flyer Sign.	Facebook, IG, Pinterest, LinkedIn, LINE@, Tiktok, Twitter, YouTube, Expo events, and Flyer Sign.)	B2C (1 Marketplace, 3 social media, Retail Store)
Popularity rating (Instagram Followers,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IG: 9615 Greview: 4,9 (395 Reviews) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IG: 2736 Greview: 4,5 (4 Reviews) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IG: 22.400 Greview: 5.0 (3 Reviews) Marketplace: 5,0 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IG: 7889 Greview: 4,4 (68 Reviews)

Company Aspect	PMU	Alkes Hidup Bahagia	Hygea Sumber Bintang	Klinik Apotik Ibnu Rusyd
Google Review Rating, Marketplace rating)	Marketplace: 4.9 (3257 Reviews)	Marketplace: 4.9 (8 Reviews)	(36 Reviews)	Marketplace: 5,0 (1 Reviews)
Complimentary Service	Pharmacies and Collaborative Clinics	N/A	Clean care and laundry	Independent Clinics
Distribution Channel	B2B and B2C (Google Ads, Marketplace, 8 social media, Retail-store Number 1 ranked Local SEO, and Website)	B2B and B2C (2, Marketplace, 5 social media, Retail-store, and Website)	B2B and B2C (2, Marketplace, 3 social media, does not had Retail-store)	B2C (1 Marketplace, 3 social media, Retail Store)
Promotional Style	Experiential and functional benefit concepts. 751 post Instagram.	Functional benefit concepts. 1435 Post Instagram	Functional benefit concepts. 756 post Instagram.	Functional benefit concepts. 881 Post Instagram
Payment Gateway	Credit, cash, Down Payment, Transfer, and QRIS	Cash, Transfer, and QRIS	Credit, Cash, Down Payment, Transfer	Cash, Transfer, and QRIS
Pricing Comparison (e.g.: sensi duckbill)	IDR 141.999, -	IDR 139.999, -	IDR 165.000, -	IDR 175.000, -

Here's a summary of the competition analysis based on the table above:

1. Other competitors have invested in digital marketing
2. PMU distributes its products aggressively in several online marketplaces, as evidenced by the number of marketplaces where they are available,
3. In terms of Instagram followers, PMU is not in the number one position but in terms of customer acquisition PMU is quite good as evidenced by the high number of reviews
4. PMU and two other competitors had websites for firm information, as well as e-commerce for purchasing the items. However, on the PMU website, the commerce function is just used to explore goods; transactions cannot be completed on it.

4.2 Internal Analysis

For internal analysis author will perform on some analysis VRIO/RBV (Table 5), Segmentation, Targeting, Positioning (STP) (Table 6), and Internal Audit Marketing activities. For VRIO analysis on the table below, and resources are categorized as temporary competitive advantages (TCA) rather than competitive parity (CP) and sustained competitive advantages (SCA).

Table 5. VRIO Analysis (Internal)

Resources	V	R	I	O	Total Score	Implications
Tangible						
PMU had competitive advantage asset assets for their business)	1	1	1	1	4	SCA
Number of human resources and well Competence	1	1	1	1	4	SCA
Marketing Network	1	0	1	1	3	TCA
Research and development facility	1	0	0	1	2	TCA
Workshop capacity	1	1	0	1	3	TCA
Completed SKU product	1	0	1	0	3	TCA
promedikamitrautama.com for all-in-one website	1	0	0	1	2	TCA
Intangible Resources						
The company's brand	1	1	1	1	4	SCA
Well maintained stakeholders-customer relationship	1	1	0	0	2	TCA
Well maintained and exclusive stakeholder-supplier relationship	1	0	1	1	2	TCA
Well maintained stakeholder-government relationship	1	1	0	1	4	TCA
Well maintained stakeholder-community relationship	1	0	0	0	0	CP

For business operations, such as branch offices or the use of technology for daily use operations, which can be seen in the process of digitization, there are two resource points that can be considered a long-term competitive advantage is categorized to SCA. As a small company that is not too big. currently PMU has 18 employees who have different skills and they do not hesitate to help each other departments for the betterment of the company. In general, this will be a sustainable benefit for the business. For some complementary assets owned by PMU such as marketing networks, research / workshop facilities, product completeness, and websites this is valuable for companies,

PMU as a distributor of medical devices does not actually have its own manufactured products. Therefore, the author did not include mentioning the product's uniqueness asset as an asset in this analysis. But that does not mean that PMU does not have advantages in the field of products. The superiority of the product on PMU lies in the number of variations of products sold. nearly 2000 products of various medical device functions are sold by the company during its operation and from this capability make PMU more favored by consumers. Maybe in a short-run PMU will achieve TCA. but this is easily imitated by competitors, especially competitors who have large capitals. Next, discuss on intangible assets. Starting from the company brand. PMU has had a good reputation since its establishment in 2012 and continues to develop itself and add many of its clients, until 2020 with the pressure caused by the pandemic as its trigger, PMU began to massively market their products with digital market approach. Obviously, the reputation of this brand requires a lot of time and costs, so it is not necessarily that competitors can imitate this advantage. Therefore, these advantages include SCA. It is because of this experience that PMU gets several benefits of intangible resources such as relationships between customers, communities, suppliers, and government that are well maintained. some of these resources Indirectly this becomes a support for PMU's business processes. The advantage of this type of resource is short-run or time-limited. For this reason, researchers categorize this resource as a competitive parity and temporary competitive advantage

Table 6. STP Analysis (Internal)

Segmentation	Targeting	Positioning
B2C or Business to Consumer is a form of transaction that occurs between one company to consumer or another as wholesaler, rather than between a company and a business consumer. As an example, in the case of the corporate which is a wholesaler, manufacturer, Partnership Corporate (Drugstore Pharmacy and Clinic) SME: CV & Incorporated, Educational Institutions, and Government	PMU target demographic is widely in the range of adults aged 18 to 44. Social This profile is characterized as follows: Lower and medium class They are generally price sensitive in this social class	PMU goal is to become the first of mind medical device company that comes to mind in the people of East Kalimantan. Especially when they search quickly using Google with keywords " " "East Kalimantan medical device store"

To find out the marketing activities that PMU has carried out during their operation, an internal audit is required. Several internal audits in this study will be carried out Social Media Auditing, Paid Advertising, Content Auditing, SEO auditing.

Figure 4. Facebook and Instagram impression 2021-2022

As shown in Figure 4, social media is one of the media used by PMU. Social media marketing has become the most dominant mode for companies to reach their customers. Instagram and Facebook are applications that are widely used by users at a young age. Most young people also say that social media marketing is very effective. PMU using social media such as Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, and Pinterest, to increase product knowledge and encourage purchases. Published social media content can be in the form of product knowledge and special price promotions or discounts. Product knowledge focuses on introducing new product medical device products, which can be in the form of photos or videos introducing the characteristics of these products. Also, dynamics of the Covid-19 variant are depicted in the fluctuation on the graph during 2021-2022. which impacts PMU Social media. First, Alpha variants peak from end of 2020 to March 2021, then after Alpha variant, Delta peaked in July to September 2021. After Delta variant ended in March 2022, the other variant reappears with the Omicron variant on April 2022 to June 2022.

and the of variant penetration in Indonesia is Delmicron, is a further alternative to omicron. Delmicron is not a new coronavirus variation like Alpha, Beta, and other strains. It is a hybrid of the two strains currently in existence, Omicron and Delta. The impact of this variant was not too severe, because the people at that time had been given the vaccine and were resistant enough for immunity, but still when this new variant appeared, precisely from July to the end of November 2022, the community experienced a slightly

panic which eventually caused the search for information about medical devices company and that content marketing related to be quite up. This variant caused an uptrend for several months which was also shown through search data via Pinterest and LinkedIn on PMU profile insight. Here's supporting data for 2022 insight that supports the seasonal trend of Delmicron variants Figure 5

Figure 5. Pinterest (left) and LinkedIn (Right) insight in 2022

For paid advertising in Figure 4.6 shown one of the posts used as an advertisement by PMU on Instagram. From Ad Insights, this ad has reached 37,397 people (the number of people who saw this post); 33 content interactions (can be like, comment, save, share and reply); 272 ad clicks (number of people who clicked on the post/ad); 60 profile activities (Number of users who have visited the Instagram profile). The objective of social media ads is to promote the products, and can be achieved with this ad.

Figure 6. Instagram Paid Advertising insight

for organic content created by PMU, the findings show the content created by the PMU on Figure 7 (left) it features conceptual designs, large fonts, highlight products based on categories, and some of the content there are static images and dynamic moving videos. Based on research conducted by researchers during the study. the content created by PMU is quite different benchmark to the competitor shown in Figure 7 (right). PMU has its own uniqueness compared to some other competitors.

Figure 7. PMU overall organic content

Since the beginning of 2023, precisely when this research took place. PMU also uploaded formats suitable for Instagram Reels. This content should ideally contain at least 1 minute of dense information to be effective and if it is more then it will look boring and, appear monotonous and unattractive. This video targets users who like to surf to swipe the app as the target user. Along with this study, researchers found quite interesting findings regarding the use of vertical video content on Instagram (Reels). These findings take analytical data in January, the findings are shown in the Figure below 8

Figure 8. PMU overall reels insight

Reels achieve more impressions than the image content that PMU usually posts in previous years. Here are some of the things you can take

- Compared to the previous month (December-January). January and February since using account reels reached up to 174%, interactions 103%, and follower totals up 0.4%
- Content reels reach more of a non-PMU audience of non-followers, with a ratio of (85:15) percent which is 23,900 non-followers and 2778 is PMU followers
- Accounts interaction based by location conclude and show that Balikpapan, Samarinda, and Tenggarong as the nearest cities where the branches and retail offices of PMU still dominate the most, because store affordability is still a consideration for customers in buying goods. Of the total 419 accounts interacting, Samarinda received 38.2%, Jakarta 5.6%, Tenggarong 4.8%, and 3.4% from Balikpapan.
- Interactions from reels increase by 398% from 781 content interactions. With 371 detailed likes, 11 comments, 79 content saves frequency, and 224 content times

One of the contributors to traffic organically from search engine is Google Business Profile (GBP). Local Search Engine Optimization (Local SEO) is the process of enhancing business entity presence to increase business from local searches. This search is conducted on a variety of search engines, however local SEO concentrates on optimizing for Google users. Because everyone uses search engines to find local companies, local SEO is essential. In the Figure 9, for the keywords “Toko Alkes Samarinda” and Promedika Mitra Utama is on the first suggestion from google search compared to other companies. By the number of the reviews, PMU also has the highest reviews, which might increase the consumer's trust in the company.

Figure 9. PMU search on google

The data in the table 6 below shows that these keywords have managed to reach more than half of the total audience volume for each keyword (look at the potential percentage column). This certainly can be a reference for companies to be able to use these keywords to improve branding, expand product diversification, and become a business opportunity for those who want to become partners with another brand to boost sales of product (Refer to One med product brand).

Table 6. STP Analysis (Internal)

No	Most Searched Keyword	Avg Monthly Search Volume	PMU GBP Search Queries (Nov 2022)	Searched/ Reached Percentage (%)	Potential Percentage (%)	Google Search Ranking
1	Promedika Mitra Utama	390	233	59,7%	40,3%	1
2	Toko Alat Kesehatan Samarinda	260	131	50,4%	49,6%	1
3	Agen Shopee Samarinda	260	80	30,8%	69,2%	25
4	Toko Safety Samarinda	480	74	15%	85%	18
5	One med Samarinda	6,600	40	0,6%	99,4%	1

The keyword testing on table 6 used is "Toko alat kesehatan" and several health products sold by Promedika, located in Samarinda. Based on the picture above, results from the search recommends Promedika as a medical device store with an average rating of first and third shown overall impressions reached by PMU. From data above author conclude, by regularly updating the content of Google business Profile, PMU successfully maintain their presence in Google Search Engine. From the data at Figure 8, in the period June-Nov 2022, there are 27,839 people who saw the PMU profile. Where 61% of those people find the profile through google search (mobile), and 26% find the profile through Google Maps (profile). The 2 top keywords for PMU are the branded keywords, which mean the awareness of the brand itself is already good. While for those who might not know about the brand, find

marinda

Figure 10. Overall insight performance on PMU GBP

And the last audit is online marketplace activities, the data taken in this study is data from the Tokopedia and Shopee platforms.

Figure 10. My Shopee insight

The image above is one of the features at Shopee. My Business by Shopee is a tool in the Seller Center to view overall store performance and sales data. In the main criteria section, there was a summary of key metrics such as sales, orders, conversion rates, total visitors, and product views in a year. All metrics are likely to improve compared to last year, including canceled orders which should be decreased. Conversion Rate is the number of shoppers divided by the number of shop visitors during the time from January until October 2022, which is 4.35%. The number is still below 10%, it should still be optimized better to get results

Figure 11. Tokopedia sales insight

Figure 11 shown Tokopedia sales interpret in Graph, PMU sales revenue in Tokopedia still rose in the early years and started to have a downtrend from February 2022 until April 2022 because the omicron phase was done. The sales started to increase again in May, as Promedika started to shift their focus to exercise and therapy tools. Though, the total number in sales in 2022 (period Jan-Nov 22).

4.3 Proposed Marketing Strategy

SWOT stands for Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats. Strengths and Weaknesses describe the organization's internal environment which firm has the control of them. Strengths are the good things that help the business, and Weaknesses are the things inside the business that keep it from performing at its best. Opportunities and threats describe the outside environment of the organization. Table 7 is the result of finding and planning the to reduce threats, take advantage of opportunities, exploit strengths, and remove weaknesses for 2023 planning.

Table 7. TOWS Analysis (Internal)

TOWS Matrix	STRENGTH (S)	WEAKNESS (W)
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Distinct brand identity 2. Comparatively less expensive than the competitor 3. Complete service and product SKU 4. PMU has a large enough customer database to distribute information 5. Massively Digital Presence in every platform (social media, local SEO, and online marketplace 6. Have their own offices and retail that are quite large and noticeable in the middle of the city 7. Had a good reputation when deliver value on service satisfy and Flexibility in responding to 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Inconsistency in carrying out marketing efforts 2. Highly fixed cost for big asset (Office Building/Ruko) 3. Since the pandemic ended, PMU has lacked the funds to develop their internal processes. because turnover drops 4. There are certifications that PMU has not done, legally this will be a small risk 5. Because there are too many products SKU that PMU sells, PMU finds it difficult to marketing it that products and maintain it.

	<p>consumer feedback inquiries and requests</p> <p>8. Have a good relationship with supplier and Community</p>	
<p>OPPORTUNITY (O)</p> <p>1. Innovations in technology that facilitate the company's ability to contact and serve consumers (e.g.: various online marketplace growth and ERP)</p> <p>2. Short video content, potential to boost the audience (Shorts, Reels, and TikTok).</p> <p>3. Through the government's stunting program, PMU targets puskesmas and posyandu (Public Health Sector) as potential target customers to achieve additional revenue and customer.</p>	<p>AGGRESSIVE STRATEGY (S-O)</p> <p>1. Expand the sales coverage to another region district/suburb (S1, S4, S5, O3)</p> <p>2. Optimizing not well digital platform like Bukalapak, Blibli, Goalkes. and etc except Tokopedia Shopee (competitive marketplace) to attract unreach/new customers (S5, O1)</p> <p>3. Create pricing strategy to increase traffic of marketplace visitor (S2, O1, O2)</p> <p>4. Increasing the intensity of conventional advertising to attract more customers. for example, by participating in exhibitions more often (S7, S8, O3)</p>	<p>REVERSAL STRATEGY (W-O)</p> <p>1. Develop informative and educational content to promote PMU products and services online (W1, O1)</p> <p>2. Hire skilled marketers to in charge marketing activates and communicators to grow the team. (W1, W5, O1, O2)</p> <p>3. PMU should use short vertical video to develop audience-targeted content (e.g.: IG reels) (W1, W3, O2)</p>
<p>THREAT (T)</p> <p>1. New and tighter regulation for medical device industry</p> <p>2. 2023 Global economic slowdown that leads to people's purchasing power towards goods falls</p> <p>3. Competition with Multinational and local service companies</p> <p>4. Similar product on the open market was less expensive.</p> <p>5. Price increases from the supplier</p>	<p>DIVERSIFICATION STRATEGY (S-T)</p> <p>1. Retain existing customers by providing continuous after-sales product support (S4, S7, S8, T3)</p> <p>2. To maintain a competitive advantage, maintain the product that have value proposition (S4, T4, T5)</p> <p>3. Increasing the company's reputation as a reliable supplier of medical devices. PMU emphasizes that all work and projects are handled by PMU before (S1, S4, S5, T3)</p> <p>4. Obtaining the best distributor/supplier pricing for</p>	<p>DEFENSIVE STRATEGY (W-T)</p> <p>1. Examine inventory management to ensure optimum stock availability, particularly for products that will not be sold again after pandemic (W2, W5, T2, T4)</p> <p>2. Rethink the pricing strategy approach for consumers, also including offer promotion campaigns (W1, W3, T4, T5)</p> <p>3. Offer product bundles to make it seem (as if) to attract getting a better deal (W3, W5, T3, T5)</p>

	customer benefits (S2, S3, T4, T5) 5. Offering replacement products for the product that customer hard to find (S3, T4, T5)	
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The S-O approach is also known as the Aggressive Growth Strategy. It is a strategy that uses the corporate's internal strengths to capitalize on external opportunities such as expanding market share and increasing revenues through pricing strategy. The W-T strategy is a defensive plan that tries to reduce weaknesses and threats as much as possible. Companies that have both internal and external problems are in a not good situation in short or long run. Reversal strategy (WO) and diversification strategy (ST) are aimed to enhance weaknesses by exploiting some internal and external chances to reduce threats by continuously and maintain on strengths. The next step, based on some of the findings from the internal, external, and TOWS analysis, it below is some proposed marketing strategy that can be implemented PMU for a few years. By utilizing the elements of the marketing mix, PMU can both meet the expectation of customers need and establish a more personalized position in their minds. It will be involving the 7P Product, Price, Place and Promotion, People, Process, and physical evidence. and, to capture sustainable competitive advantage PMU must be focus on Differentiation Focus and Cost Leadership as a state on Porter Generic strategy on show in table 8 is because by minimizing the costs incurred in providing value (product or service) to a customer, PMU can help maintain the capital into a differentiation focus. This means by making some of product unique or special, compared to other competitors or substitute products, it will be good for PMU to maintain the PMU position in this highly disrupted market condition.

Table 8. Proposed Overall strategy

Key Points	Finding aspect	Recommendation/proposed strategy
Marketing Mix	Promotion:	1. Online and Offline advertising in 2 (two) semesters in 2023 1.1 Product knowledge ads (Semester 1): Form of content advertising: Instagram ads (Paid) and Instagram Reels (Organic) 1.2 Marketplace Ads (semester 2): Shopee/Tokopedia ads (Paid) and Instagram Reels (Evaluation From semester 1) (Organic) 1.3 Offline Campaign (Semester 1): socialization to public health sector and government 1.4 Offline Campaign (Semester 2): Joining public exhibition to reaches more customer (college students in the medical field)
	Product	1. Content matrix and pillar to mapping the content 2. Create image and video content to increase awareness (Poster)(Video/IG reels): - Discounted product to boost sales - Virality, Quiz/game to boost sales - Tips and Trick (How to use product/product feature) - Educative information (Basic daily information about healthcare e.g.: trend report or infographic) - For desired and action content: will be checklist starter pack, event, or demo videos - Stunting program product - Medical device product that college student need
	Place	To anticipate losses opportunity for customer, PMU applies indent-preorder product if customer want to wait for a while
	Price	BATNA Negotiating strategy for incentive to customer. to increase traffic
	People	1. Create SOP to anticipate conflicting rules and job

Key Points	Finding aspect	Recommendation/proposed strategy
		2. For additional human resources, PMU can create internship program to take advantage efficient and less expensive
	Process	1. Content planning calendar 2. Marketing monthly report 3. Marketing annually reports
	Physical Evidence	Business card, catalog, brochure, company profile personalized to the need for corona replacement goods like stunting programs, and medical devices for college students in the health sector
Porter Generic	Differentiation Focus	1. For market penetration, the East Kalimantan Area is the target market for PMU in the next few years, which is a fragmented market that has a relatively mass-market market number of populations overall, but not in mean national scale (Indonesia).
	Cost Leadership	2. PMU makes its business different from those of its competitors by coming up with a set of service lines that address current problems and meet customer needs. For example, by presenting medical device repair services, bringing more unique products to online sales, and creating more personalized content 3. For a next few year cost leadership can be applied for PMU. Healthcare industry has led to a price war situation because since the Covid-19 Corona Pandemic, quite a lot of people and micro retailer looking for an opportunity and have seen this sector, so it is not impossible, competitors will appear a lot in this business.

Some of the prominent marketing strategy summaries above answer some of the research questions asked on the business issue. A following for the first research question, what is proper proposed marketing strategy for PMU to optimizer their sales. As shown on Table 8. The proposed marketing strategy will be on offline/online activities in 2 (two) semesters in 2023. The campaign will be carried out by online ads, organic campaigns, and offline campaign. For the online ads in the first semester, the content will focus on showing the product's knowledge using Instagram ads and Reels. While in the second semester PMU will utilize 4 types of ads which are Instagram ads, Tokopedia ads, Reels and Shopee ads to drive the audience to make a purchase through PMU WhatsApp or directly to the marketplace. As for the Instagram ads, PMU will use click-to-web types of ads, where the audience will be directed to PMU link tree, so they can later choose which channel that they want to use whether contact via WhatsApp to admin sales or visit the marketplace. As for the marketplace, PMU will utilize search ads, it will increase the product visibility when the customers are searching for specific products. Also, for reels PMU will start evaluating the video Reels they made in semester 1 to be input in semester 2. in the hope of reaching even more audiences. So that it is in accordance with the objective in semester 2, boost sales.

Figure 11. Marketing Plan in 2023

For second question, what is proper content for PMU corresponds to their target market Also, content that PMU can create will be context on 1. Tips. Educative, demo, desired, event or and checklist medical devices in initial year for build awareness, and for the last year (Semester 2) will be Discounted Product, Virality, Quiz/game in the end of year to boost sales as shown on content marketing matrix on Figure 12

Figure 12. Content Marketing Matrix of PMU

Of course, this great theme will have every piece in the discussion. This big theme will be divided into 3 on the content pillar. The Content Pillar is substantive and informative content on a particular topic or theme that can be broken down into many derivative parts, sections, and materials. PMU divides content into 3 pillars, namely knowledge paradise, inspiration paradise and buyer paradise. As for the proportion of content pillars, for the first semester, it will be heavier to knowledge paradise and inspiration paradise, while the portion of buyer paradise is only 20% of the total content created in a month. Meanwhile, in the second half the content will be heavier in the paradise of inspiration and buyers to drive sales. Details described as shown in Figure 13

Medical Supply Paradise			
Content Pillars	Knowledge Paradise	Inspiration Paradise	Buyer Paradise
Content Topics	PMU will share all knowledge related to the products available at their store and the updated news related to medical supply.	PMU will share content that inspire the audience to own a good and useful medical supply for their practice.	PMU will share about all offerings available that will drive the audience to make a purchase.
Content Types	Webinar, Trend Report and Infographics, Product feature, Virality, Quiz, Game	Checklist, Event, Demo videos, Rating/Review	Sale, Bundling Package, Voucher Code, Limited Offerings.
First Semester (Content Proportion)	40%	40%	20%
Second Semester (Content Proportion)	20%	40%	40%

Table 8 Content Pillar of PMU

For the third research question, what is the right measuring tool to monitor and evaluate the results of marketing activities. The right tool to measure marketing activities as discussed in the proposed strategy is to create monthly marketing reports as shown on Figure

13 (left) that are recapitulated into annuals. and a draft content calendar on Figure 13 (right). Then to monitor marketing to fit the right track can be done by making SOPs immediately, Brand Guidelines, and Annual. On Figure 13 (Bottom)

Figure 13. Marketing Report Spreadsheet (left) Content Calendar (right), Marketing Report and Brand Guideline (bottom)

For the fourth research question, PMU does not yet have a structured marketing plan to optimize their sales to recommend implementation plans for PMU defining strategies. Regarding the proposals that have been carried out, it has been discussed before. There are around 22 proposed strategy that can be done in 2023 complete with PIC, estimates, and when the month should be carried out the strategy. In addition to the proposed marketing planning strategies, the Author provides a spending estimate for the organization to implement each marketing strategy. This budgeting is supposed to make it easier for the company to find financial support to carry out its marketing efforts. The marketing budget planned is shown in the Figure 14 below.

No	Strategy	Cost est	PIC	2023												
				January	February	March	April	Mei	June	July	Agustus	September	Oktober	Novemeber	Desember	
1	Online advertising Product Knowledge	IDR 6 Mio	Digital Selling													
2	Marketplace Ads	IDR 6 Mio	Digital Selling													
3	Offline Campaign : Stunting Program	IDR 6 Mio	External Development													
4	Offline Campaign : Exhibition and Medical student Program	IDR 6 Mio	External Development													
5	Tips and Trick Content(Product Feature)	Part of Staff Jobdesc	Graphic/Motion, Video Staff													
6	Educative Content															
7	Discounted product campaign content															
8	Offer product bundled content															
9	Virality, Quiz/Game content															
10	Desired content															
11	Create SOP for Marketing Activities															
12	Socialize and Implement SOP															
13	Internship Program															
14	Applied Indent-preorder product policies															
15	Applied Inventory Management Policies															
16	Applied Batra Pricing Strategy Incentive															
18	Content calendar															
19	Marketing Monthly Report															
20	Marketing Annual Report															
21	Meeting and initially development web															
22	Optimizing not well platform															

Figure 14 Implementation Plan Schedule

3. CONCLUSION

There are many factors that can affect marketing planning. However, marketing planning can be used as a reference to determine better decision making, as it takes into business situational based on external, internal, and some experts in the departments of the organization. Not only from one department but involving other departments, considerations in coordination with another department like finance to budgeting and budgets entered by the company's finance team. More deeply this study is the big picture for future research. Based on the analysis of chapter 4 result and Discussion. PMU may be in a safe position among its competitors because it has invested in offline marketing and digital marketing activities long before the advancement of digital marketing is massive like this day before. regardless of the condition of other companies will experience the same risks. This paper is expected to provide an overview and context of how marketing planning can affect the business. Within the scope of SME/micro retailers themselves, marketing planning problems are not easy problems to solve. Future researchers can therefore provide interesting input on how the ever-changing industry.

REFERENCES

1. Maemunah, S. & Cuaca, H. Influence of epidemic COVID–19 on business strategy, information technology and supply chain agility to firm performance in medical device industry. *Linguistics and Culture Review* 5, (2021).
2. Sahil, M., Kaushik, I. & Kaler, A. Future of Pharma Industry and Medical Devices after Corona Pandemic. *American Journal of PharmTech Research* 11, (2021).
3. Larasati, D. N., Bustaman, U. & Pramana, S. Online Marketplace Data to Figure COVID-19 Impact on Micro and Small Retailers in Indonesia. *Indonesian Journal of Statistics and Its Applications* 5, (2021).
4. Zahra, Z. PENGARUH DYNAMIC CAPABILITIES TERHADAP FIRM PERFORMANCE PADA PT SICHA JAYA SENTOSA. (2017).
5. Chaffey Dave. Sixth Edition *Digital Marketing - Strategy, Implementation, and Practice*. www.pearson.com/uk (2016).
6. Maemunah, S. & Cuaca, H. Influence of epidemic COVID–19 on business strategy, information technology and supply chain agility to firm performance in medical device industry. *Linguistics and Culture Review* 5, (2021).
7. Sahil, M., Kaushik, I. & Kaler, A. Future of Pharma Industry and Medical Devices after Corona Pandemic. *American Journal of PharmTech Research* 11, (2021).

8. Larasati, D. N., Bustaman, U. & Pramana, S. Online Marketplace Data to Figure COVID-19 Impact on Micro and Small Retailers in Indonesia. Indonesian Journal of Statistics and Its Applications 5, (2021).
9. Zahra, Z. PENGARUH DYNAMIC CAPABILITIES TERHADAP FIRM PERFORMANCE PADA PT SICHA JAYA SENTOSA. (2017).
10. Gereffi, G. What does the COVID-19 pandemic teach us about global value chains? The case of medical supplies. Journal of International Business Policy vol. 3 Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.1057/s42214-020-00062-w> (2020).
11. Reimann, C., Carvalho, F. & Duarte, M. The influence of dynamic and adaptive marketing capabilities on the performance of portuguese smes in the b2b international market. Sustainability (Switzerland) 13, (2021).
12. Prohl-Schwenke, K. & Kleinaltenkamp, M. How business customers judge customer success management. Industrial Marketing Management 96, 197–212 (2021).
13. Hilton, B., Hajihashemi, B., Henderson, C. M. & Palmatier, R. W. Customer Success Management: The next evolution in customer management practice? Industrial Marketing Management 90, (2020).

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